

RELATION BETWEEN VISCOSITY AND GELATION OF AN IRON SILICATE SOL

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A sol of iron silicate has been prepared by the interaction of ferric chloride and sodium silicate solutions. The rate of flow of this sol at various stages of purity attained by dialysis has been measured at different pressures causing the flow and also with progressive dialysis. With dialysis the iron content has been found to decrease, but silica content remains practically constant, whilst the impurity as chloride attains a value beyond which further dialysis causes the gelation of the sol within the parchment bag.

The sol has a tendency to yield gels simply by prolonged dialysis, coagulation with suitable amounts of electrolytes, or by simply warming at a certain stage of purity. The results are significant for the measurements of the rate of flow through capillary where it is definitely shown that when the sol begins to deviate from the Poiseuille's law for fluids, either for its concentration or purity, it yields gels. Hence, the tendency of the development of the structural flow is concluded to be intimately related with the capacity for the formation of a gel from a sol.

Some colloids become more viscous when made pure by dialysis and some of these sols show an increase in viscosity, and finally they set to a firm gel on prolonged dialysis, or by coagulation with suitable electrolytes (cf. Banerji and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 148). In several publications from this laboratory (Ghosh and co-workers, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 68, 37; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 140) it has been pointed out that such sols do not obey Poiseuille's law, for the viscosity of these sols remarkably decreases with increasing shearing force. Ghosh *et al.* ascribe this to the formation of loose structure, and have termed the flow of such sols through a capillary, structural flow, which is similar to plastic flow described by Bingham ("Fluidity and Plasticity", New York, 1922). In this paper the relation of viscosity, specially from the point of view of applicability of Poiseuille's law, with the tendency of gel formation has been studied for an iron silicate sol for various stages of purity attained by dialysis, and it has been established that formation of a gel from a sol of iron silicate is possible only when the sol has developed sufficient structural flow.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ferric chloride solution (100 c.c.) having 4.3 g. atoms of chlorine per litre, diluted to 400 c.c. with distilled water, was taken to prepare the colloid. Sodium silicate solution (193.9 c.c.) having 11.092 moles of Na_2O and 12.4 moles of SiO_2 per litre was taken which had Na_2O content equivalent to the total chloride content of the 100 c.c. of the ferric chloride solution and diluted to 1550 c.c. with distilled water. This diluted sodium silicate solution was gradually added to ferric chloride solution with constant stirring. The precipitate of iron silicate formed was peptised by ferric or hydrogen ions and a yellowish red sol of iron silicate resulted. After adding 1200 c.c. of sodium silicate solution the precipitate formed refused to be peptised and a slight precipitation was visible. Hence, the sol was prepared by using lesser amount of sodium

silicate solution than the equivalent quantity. Attempts to prepare the sol containing equivalent quantity failed, as the addition of the equivalent quantity gave precipitates of iron silicate. The sol, thus prepared, contained an excess of ferric chloride and was positively charged. It was filtered through glass wool and kept for dialysis. Samples of different purities were collected and diluted twice, four times and eight times with distilled water so as to give four different concentrations of the sol. The rate of flow relative to that of water for each sample was noted at four different pressures, namely 15 cm., 30 cm., 45 cm., and 60 cm. of the water column by a modified Ostwald's viscometer, first described by Ghosh and Ayub (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 149), outline diagram of which is given in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

It consists of an Ostwald's viscometer with three additional bulbs a , c_1 , c_2 of small capacity each besides the main bulb, b , of the viscometer. These additional bulbs are to store the liquid on the both sides of the capillary and to provide sufficient time for getting the pressure applied uniformly. Three or more Winchester bottles, each about three litres capacity, are wrapped in saw dust for shielding them from the external temperature variations. The air inside them is compressed by connecting them with a large flask in which tap water flows in and creates compression. The Winchester bottles containing compressed air, acting as a source of applying pressure, are connected with a water manometer on one side and to the limb of the viscometer through a board B of stop-cocks, which provides a device for reversing the pressure in the limb of the viscometer. When the stop-cocks 2 and 5 are closed and 1 and 4 are open, the liquid flows in f_1f_2 direction, *i.e.*, the liquid flows down, while reversing the stop-cock arrangement, *i.e.*, opening 2 and 5, and closing 1 and 4, the liquid flows in the reverse direction, *i.e.*, f_2f_1 , and fills the bulb. The time taken by the liquid to go from f_1f_2 (t_1)

and then from f_2f_1 marks (t_2) are noted separately. The viscometer is kept in a thermostat. The volume of the liquid is so chosen for the viscometer that the values of t_1 and t_2 do not differ much, so that the average pressure due to the difference in the levels of the liquid in the two limbs of the viscometer is very nearly the same, and the pressure recorded on the manometer is mainly responsible for causing the flow. Measurements are made only up to such a pressure where the turbulent flow of the liquid just appears. In our case, the flow becomes turbulent if the time of flow of the volume of liquid between f_1, f_2 marks becomes less than 1 minute and 15 seconds as determined by the measurement of viscosities of standard fluids. The appropriate volume for our viscometer is 30.5 c.c. The relative viscosity of sols with respect to water is calculated by

$$\eta_s / \eta_w = \frac{1/t_{1w} + 1/t_{2w}}{1/t_{1s} + 1/t_{2s}}$$

where η_s is the viscosity of the sol at a definite temperature and pressure, η_w is the viscosity of water under the same conditions; t_{1w} and t_{2w} are the times of flow downwards and upwards respectively for water; t_{1s} and t_{2s} denote times of flow downwards and upwards respectively for the sol (cf. Jha and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 23).

The experimental results described here deal with four samples of iron silicate sols—before dialysis, after 48 hours of dialysis, 96 hours of dialysis, and 144 hours of dialysis, that is, just before seven days, five days, three days, and a day before the sol sets to a gel simply by progressive dialysis. The relative viscosities of each sample and its dilutions were measured at three different temperatures and four different pressures. Each sample was analysed for its iron, silica, and chloride contents.

TABLE I

Sol I.—Sample before dialysis.

Composition: Fe_2O_3 , 0.03332 g. mole/litre.

SiO_2 , 0.09524 „ „ „

Cl, 0.19770 g. atom/ „

Iron silicate therefore contains Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 in the ratio of 1:2.89. This sample shows coagulation with electrolytes after boiling. The coagulation gives opaque precipitates.

Pressure in water column. (P).	Temp. = 20°				Temp. = 40°			
	Sol I. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/8. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	1.181	1.101	1.015	1.014	1.180	1.104	1.046	1.027
30	1.179	1.100	1.009	1.007	1.179	1.100	1.043	1.015
45	1.172	1.086	1.009	1.007	1.157	1.096	1.036	1.014
60	1.169	1.079	1.003	1.003	1.147	1.086	1.035	1.014

Pressure in water column.	Temp. = 60°.				Temp. cooled to 60° from 20°.			
	Sol I. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/8. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I 4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol I 8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	1.414	1.029	1.074	1.035	1.375	1.162	1.016	1.016
30	1.410	1.126	1.074	1.033	1.356	1.153	1.013	1.039
45	1.392	1.106	1.058	1.030	1.352	1.153	1.010	1.007
60	1.374	1.076	1.001	1.018	1.330	1.144	1.066	1.006

TABLE II

Sol II.—Sample taken after 48 hours of dialysis.

Composition : Fe_2O_3 , 0.0312 g. mole/litre.

SiO_2 , 0.0953 ,, ,, ,,

Cl, 0.03029,, atom/l ,,

It contains Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 in the ratio of 1:3.05. The sample shows coagulation by electrolytes on warming and the precipitates become opaque red.

Pressure in water column.	Temp. = 20°.				Temp. = 40°.			
	Sol II. (η_s/η_w)	Sol II/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol II/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol II/8. (η_s/η_w)	Sol II. (η_s/η_w)	II/2. (η_s/η_w)	II/4. (η_s/η_w)	II/8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	1.300	1.035	1.014	1.010	1.262	1.140	1.038	1.030
30	1.254	1.030	1.007	1.009	1.254	1.140	1.029	1.022
45	1.240	1.021	1.006	1.000	1.254	1.139	1.027	1.019
60	1.237	1.012	1.003	1.000	1.252	1.138	1.024	1.012

Pressure in water column.	Temp. = 60°.				Temp. cooled from 60° to 20°			
	II. (η_s/η_w)	II/2. (η_s/η_w)	II/4. (η_s/η_w)	II/8. (η_s/η_w)	II. (η_s/η_w)	II/2. (η_s/η_w)	II/4. (η_s/η_w)	II/8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	1.413	1.148	1.084	1.034	1.483	1.114	1.023	1.018
30	1.396	1.131	1.078	1.023	1.469	1.110	1.022	1.012
45	1.396	1.112	1.078	1.031	1.469	1.102	1.020	1.010
60	1.394	1.109	1.066	1.019	1.450	1.102	1.012	1.006

TABLE III

Sol III.—Sample taken after 96 hours of dialysis.

Composition : Fe_2O_3 , 0.030 g. mole/litre.

SiO_2 , 0.09526 ,, ,,

Cl, 0.0083 ,, atom' ,,

Iron silicate therefore contains Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 in the ratio of 1:3.08. The sol yields gelatinous precipitates on coagulation with electrolytes.

Pressure in water column.	Temp. = 20°.				Temp. = 40°.			
	III. (η_s/η_w)	III/2. (η_s/η_w)	III/4. (η_s/η_w)	III/8. (η_s/η_w)	III. (η_s/η_w)	III/2. (η_s/η_w)	III/4. (η_s/η_w)	III/8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	1.325	1.052	1.018	1.018	1.315	1.152	1.040	1.028
30	1.312	1.046	1.017	1.017	1.320	1.148	1.035	1.028
45	1.286	1.035	1.012	1.016	1.309	1.143	1.034	1.020
60	1.280	1.032	1.007	1.006	1.286	1.136	1.030	1.017

	Temp. = 60°.				Temp. cooled from 60° to 20°.			
	III.	III/2.	III/4.	III/8.	III.	III/2.	III/4.	III/8.
15 cms.	1.394	1.147	1.042	1.028	1.493	1.086	1.048	1.031
30	1.380	1.152	1.038	1.028	1.462	1.057	1.045	1.029
45	1.366	1.148	1.035	1.022	1.452	1.052	1.040	1.029
60	1.348	1.140	1.034	1.020	1.425	1.052	1.036	1.022

TABLE IV

Sol. IV.—Sample taken after 144 hours of dialysis.

Composition: Fe_2O_3 , 0.02907 g. moles/litre.

SiO_2 , 0.09524 ,, ,,

Cl, 0.0083 ,, atom/ ,,

Iron silicate therefore contains Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 in the ratio of 1:3.27. The sol yields good gels which are transparent, on coagulation with electrolytes, or by heating up to 65° within 5 to 10 minutes.

Pressure in water column.	Temp. = 20°.				Temp. = 40°.			
	Sol IV. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/8. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/2. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/4. (η_s/η_w)	Sol IV/8. (η_s/η_w)
15 cms.	2.767	1.264	1.028	1.029	2.843	1.287	1.098	1.043
30	2.639	1.254	1.023	1.023	2.665	1.274	1.096	1.046
45	2.585	1.242	1.022	1.022	2.525	1.266	1.093	1.040
60	2.521	1.223	1.002	1.016	2.393	1.266	1.093	...

	Temp. = 60°.				Temp. cooled from 60° to 20°.			
	Sol IV.	Sol IV/2.	Sol IV/4.	Sol IV/8.	IV.	IV/2.	IV/4.	IV/8.
15 cms.	No flow	3.216	1.263	Complete pptn. but no gelation.	The whole vol. set to a firm gel.	32.280	1.410	—
30	...	2.507	1.241	...	..	2.856	1.335	—
45	...	1.997	1.248	...	..	2.616	1.203	—
60	87.44	1.697	1.248	...	..	2.423	1.266	—

The sol IV being sufficiently pure shows large variations of η_s/η_w with changes in the pressure causing flow. Hence, this sol with remarkable structural flow can easily be coagulated with electrolytes and is seen to yield gels at room temperature. The cataphoretic coagulation under suitable condition also yields gels. The water associated with a certain volume of sol in gelation, that is, the dilution up to which this sol shows gelation after coagulation with a fixed concentration of ammonium sulphate, is shown in the following table.

TABLE V

$N/100$. Ammonium sulphate = 0.7 c.c. Water added = 0.3 c.c. Total vol. of the electrolyte (used in each case) = 1.0 c.c.

Volume of sol IV.	Vol. of water added.	Nature of precipitate.
2.0 c.c.	0.0 c.c.	Red, transparent gel without syneresis.
1.8	0.2	Do
1.6	0.4	Do
1.4	0.6	Do; syneresis pronounced.
1.3	0.7	Gelatinous ppt.

The results obtained on analysis of different samples of the sol show that the amount of iron goes on continuously decreasing with progressive dialysis. The amount of silica remains practically constant throughout the dialysis. The amount of chloride ion decreases quickly and finally reaches a constant value, which cannot be removed by further dialysis. Ferric chloride at earlier stages passes out which is in excess. Finally Fe_2O_3 and SiO_2 ratio becomes 1 : 3.27. Further dialysis leads to the formation of the sol as a transparent gel.

Iron silicate shows the evidence of the variation in the value of η_s/η_w at different pressures effecting the flow from the very beginning (cf. Dissert., Heidelberg; *Phil. Mag.*, 1903, 6, 374). These variations become more and more pronounced as the purity of the sol increases. For example, at 20°, sol I shows a change of 1020% in the rate of flow for the variation of the pressure from 15 cm. to 60 cm. of water column. This change in the rate of flow increases to 9.7% for the variation in pressure causing flow, from 15 cm. to 60 cm. of water column in case of sol IV which is much pure for practically the same concentration of the sol. By prolonged dialysis the viscosity as well as the structural flow of the sol increases (cf. Bingham and Green, *Proc. Amer. Soc. Test. Mat.*, 1919, 19, 641) and when the structural flow becomes very prominent at a certain stage of purity, the gelation can be effected by the addition of electrolytes.

The coagulation of the sol is helped as the temperature is increased. In all cases this is seen to be true and the gelation is facilitated in cases of purer sols. In samples I, II, III, it can be seen that the amount of structural flow increases with the increase of temperature (cf. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 148, 153); in the case of sol IV it increases very remarkably. Similar results have been reported by Banerji and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) for ferric phosphate sol. At 60° sol IV sets to a gel without the addition of any electrolyte which also develops an enormous increase in the structural flow and in the so-called viscosity at that temperature.

When these sols are cooled again to 20° , there is a definite increase in the values of η_s/η_w and the increase in the structural flow can be noted by comparing the data of the sol at that temperature before heating. Coagulation and gelation, thus, are favoured by heating.

In sols which set to a gel condition by progressive dialysis, as this particular one is, it is customary to ascribe it to the increased hydration by dialysis (Prakash and Dhar, this *Journal*, 1929, 6, 391; 1930, 7, 417). After a stage of purity, the hydration of the colloid particle sets the sol to a firm gel, retaining a large volume of liquid (Satya Prakash, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 3871). If it is so, the gel formation may not be facilitated by the increase of temperature, as by heating it the hydration decreases, while it is clear from our results that the structural flow becomes more pronounced with the increase of temperature. Hence, the structure and not the hydration should be related with the phenomenon of gelation.

FIG. 2

As the sol is diluted, its structural flow and necessarily η_s/η_w are seen to decrease but up to twice its dilution the decrease is not so great as it occurs in diluting the sol to 4 or 8 times. Our results show that the tendency of gelation is also seen to decrease by the addition of electrolytes. In the sol IV it is seen that the structural flow is prominent for the sol IV/2, and for sol IV/4 it becomes practically insignificant. The results show that the sol IV, when diluted twice, gives a gel, but when diluted four times only gelatinous precipitates are seen after coagulation, which shows undoubtedly that the structural flow and the tendency of gelation are seen to decrease with dilution.

It can be concluded that the colloid of iron silicate under investigation has got the structural flow from the very beginning which increases with purity. After a certain stage of purity the sol can be transformed to a gel by simple heating, by cataphoresis, by progressive dialysis, or by adding electrolytes under suitable conditions.

In Fig. 2 changes in the values of η_s/η_w against the concentration of the sols are plotted. One fact will be seen clearly from the curves that as the sols become purer and begin yielding gelatinous precipitates with increasing purity, there is always a sudden increase in the values of η_s/η_w after a certain concentration say, when it is diluted 4 times. Hence, these curves considerably deviate from the simple linear relationship of the concentration and viscosity of the sol as is expected from the simple equation of Einstein, $\eta_s = \eta_w(1 + k\phi)$, where k is a constant and represents the concentration, and the viscosity of the sol of this type is common to all lyophilic sols which have a tendency to yield gels. In several communications from this laboratory, this behaviour has been associated to the development of a structure and it will be seen from the curves that for the sol IV the increment in the values of η_s/η_w becomes remarkable, increasing from 1.028 to 2.767 when the concentration of the sol becomes 8 times with respect to the former one. This indicates a tendency of the sol to form gels, and as has been already pointed out, the sol IV yields firm transparent gels only up to twice its dilution.

In the sol-gel transformation, not only the hydration of the colloid particles but a development of loose structure, as recorded by the values of η_s/η_w at variable pressure, is of great importance and it shows a direct relation to the gelation tendency of the sol. Even where the hydration is not likely to increase, the sol yields a good gel if the sol shows a pronounced structural flow.